

DTO-BioFlow

Integration of biodiversity monitoring
data into the Digital Twin Ocean

D1.2 Risk Management Plan, M6

29/02/2024

Lead Beneficiary: Seascope Belgium

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D1.2 – Risk Management Plan

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0.2	27/09/2023	Nathalie Tonné (SSBE)	Finalising draft for upload to Teams for access by partners during Kick-off Meeting
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Disclaimer

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1. Introduction

This document presents the Risk Management Plan, which includes a risk register that identifies, prioritises and responds to potential risks across the project. This deliverable is a living document that will be updated at six-monthly intervals by the DTO-BioFlow Steering Committee.

At the time of reporting in M6, the total number of risks identified is 23 (Annex 1). Some of these risks were identified during the project proposal stage and have since been reviewed; additional information on their potential impact was added and the mitigation measures further elaborated. Each of these is described in detail in the table below, as well as the actions that will be taken to mitigate the risks including the person responsible to implement them. For each risk identified, a likelihood (probability for the risk to occur) and impact (severity of the consequence to the project) for that risk are provided each on a scale of 1 to 5: from very low to very high likelihood/impact, respectively*. The combination of Likelihood and Impact determines the Risk Exposure Index Value (Annex 1).

1.1. Legend likelihood and impact, and Risk Exposure Index Value

*Level 1: Very low likelihood/impact

Level 2: Low likelihood/impact

Level 3: Medium likelihood/impact

Level 4: High likelihood/impact

Level 5: Very high likelihood/impact

Table 1. Risk Exposure Index Value. The calculation of Likelihood multiplied by the Impact gives overall risk exposure level (coded red, amber, or green according to pre-determined threshold values, which are indicated below the table).

Likelihood	5	10	15	20	25
	4	8	12	16	20
	3	6	9	12	15
	2	4	6	8	10
	1	2	3	4	5
	Severity/Impact				

Risk level and mitigation action

Low risk level (1-4): no mitigation measures are needed, no risk on the further implementation of the project.

Medium risk level (5-15): mitigation measures are needed and should be implemented within a reasonable period of time.

High risk level (16-25): risk would block current and other activities and impact the entire project. There is a strong need for mitigation measures to be put in place as soon as possible. Project Officer should be contacted.

2. Monitoring and maintenance of risk register

The risk register will be maintained as a live document online in the DTO-BioFlow MS Teams/Sharepoint platform, to:

- i) Update the currently identified risks as the project evolves, if necessary, in terms of their likelihood, severity and corresponding mitigating actions (in agreement with the relevant WP lead and Project Management Team);

- ii) Ensure that any mitigating actions that may be deemed necessary are taken in a timely manner by the WP lead or the relevant partner (as identified by the WP lead);
- iii) Identify and add any new risks that may arise in response to unforeseen circumstances as the project evolves (in agreement with the relevant WP lead and Project Management Team).

Seascope Belgium will be responsible for maintaining and monitoring the risk register and bringing it to the attention of the Coordinator and the responsible WP Leads for action via a dedicated recurring agenda item at all Steering Committee (StC) meetings. At each StC, the risks will be reviewed and potential follow-up actions (if any) will be defined.

Should action be required between Steering Committee meetings, this will be raised with the Project Management Team and Steering Committee and appropriate action taken depending on the level of the risk as indicated above in section 1.

3. Risk register

Table 1: Overview of identified risks.

Risk #	Risk Description	Risk owner	Likelihood (1-5)	Severity/ Impact (1-5)	Risk Exposure Index Value (likelihood x impact)	Potential impact	Proposed mitigation measures	Date of risk registered (dd/mm/yyyy)	Date of risk revision (dd/mm/yyyy)	Review and follow-up action required	Status (active/closed)
1	Low commitment of the partners to the project plan and deadlines	WP1	3	5	15	Delays/deviations in the delivery of Deliverables and achievement of Milestones. Missed reporting deadlines for EU. Project doesn't achieve all Deliverables in lifetime of project. Reputational risk to partners. Funding interrupted.	Continual monitoring of performance by well-staffed PMT and experienced WP leads. Maintaining clear communication with partners and with the European Commission.	01/09/2023			Active
2	Low numbers of data submission to the calls; delays in or partial delivery of data submissions from data grant holders	WP2	3	4	12	Delays/deviations in the delivery of related Deliverables and achievement of related Milestones.	Thorough follow-up of grant holder progress through regular meetings to discuss progress and possible problems. Review of grant holders' geographical and technical backgrounds between the first and second call to highlights shortcomings. Final payment of the grant will only be done after acceptance of the data for integration, to stimulate timely submission. The data grant holders will be trained through workshops in how to properly submit data	01/09/2023			Active

3	Limited access to high-performance computing (HPC) infrastructure	WP3	5	3	15	Delays in implementation of workflows and analysis of data which will, in turn, cause delays in the creation of data products and product incorporation into the DTO.	Develop a list of the available HPC resources from the partners. In case of failure to adhere to the planned resources, turn to the available HPCs of project partners. DTO-BioFlow partnership includes multiple partners who are members of EuroHPC, as well as partners that have their own HPC facilities (e.g. UGOT, LifeWatch ERIC, CSC, HCMR, IT4I@VSB).	01/09/2023			Active
4	Test casing failures/delays in the field and/or laboratory	WP3	2	1	2	Delays in completion of subtask 1, which will not impact however the data flows into the DTO.	Detailed and consistent monitoring of all field and laboratory procedures, so as to allow troubleshooting as early as possible. Test casing will be performed in few and small-scale level cases before implementing to large-scale monitoring schemes.	01/09/2023			Active
5	Delay in obtaining available data from observation networks	WP3	2	4	8	Delays in data ingestion into the DTO. However, it is highly unlikely that all the observation networks and projects will delay in their data provision simultaneously.	Exploit contacts with other observatory networks, which have already been established through strong partner networks and contacts. Access to DTO-BioFlow resources will incentivise networks. Exploit data and data products from the other sources identified in the Blueprint.	01/09/2023			Active
6	Data management and modelling tasks become too complex for transfer to DTO	WP4	2	5	10	Automation will not be complete and some data management and/or analysis tasks have to be done externally or offline.	The DUC will be reduced in complexity by dividing modelling tasks into smaller workflows which include less parameters per analytical task.	01/09/2023			Active

7	WP3 data products are not good enough to answer the scientific question	WP4	1	3	3	Use cases will not showcase the added value of the DTO.	Co-creation with users will ensure relevance. Task will be modified to demonstrate the potential of the missing data, specify the data gaps, and test the DTO infrastructure	01/09/2023			Active
8	Demonstrators are not compelling for external users	WP4	1	3	3	End user will not use (or contribute to) DTO resources.	External science networks and stakeholders are included in the DUC design. Regular revision by external users. Deep integration with sister projects (BioDT, Iliad, etc).	01/09/2023			Active
9	Disconnect with WP2/3/4. No reusable tools can be defined.	WP5	1	5	5	DTO-BioFlow results would be lower than expected. Results would obviously be better if the project is able to leverage existing tools than if it has to develop new ones.	Structural approach in WP2/3/4 for ensuring well described process & Tools. (Activity for describing is in WP2/3/4). Best practices & templates from already running projects (BioDT / Iliad) will be re-used.	01/09/2023			Active
10	No cohesion possible between other projects. Various projects & initiatives each choose their own standards.	WP5	1	5	5	No cohesion would significantly lower the impact of the project by limiting replicability of scalability of the solutions developed in DTO-BioFlow.	Many of the partners involved in the consortium have leading roles in the relevant other running projects. A tight link will be kept with related initiatives through joint meetings and by inviting key players in the EAB, expert and matchmaking events.	01/09/2023			Active
11	No access to infrastructure. LUMI / EuroHPC are not available	WP5	1	5	5	Use cases capacities limited by the infrastructure they have access to.	HPC infrastructures already works. Project has multiple partners who are members of LUMI/EuroHPC (CSC, IT4I@VSB)	01/09/2023			Active
12	Existing code too old / inflexible. Software used by other WPs is simply too old to translate to modern technology.	WP5	1	5	5	Impossibility to use some Software and/or loss of time trying to translate too/old/inflexible code.	A selection process will be made to only convert software that is feasible and sensible.	01/09/2023			Active

13	No adoption or innovation towards continuous ecology. Researchers stick to existing data, tools and models.	WP5	1	5	5	This would significantly lower the impact of the project by limiting replicability of the solutions developed in DTO-BioFlow.	KPIs created to measure re-usability, which is a key focus. WP2/3/4 activities will (co-)develop on existing tools/services so adoption becomes more likely.	01/09/2023		Active
14	Insufficient level of DTO computational resources	WP5	1	3	3	This would result in having to set priorities on which use case can make use of computational resources. Some, ranking low, may not have the opportunity to access it.	By prioritizing & properly scoping datasets & use-cases we should easily be able to prevent over-use of resources. Alternatively, if a use-case really does require more than available resources, additional resources could be allocated.	01/09/2023		Active
15	Incompatibility of developed services with current DTO frameworks	WP5	1	3	3	This would create some lock-in and potential silos. This would also prevent the project of using already existing data or tools. The result is again lower impact and reach for DTO-BioFlow.	This requires the DTO frameworks to align with each other and to align the service development with the DTO framework. The goal should be to create technology agnostic interfaces as much as possible to prevent incompatibility.	01/09/2023		Active

16	Delays in DTO framework construction in related digital twin projects	WP5	1	5	5	This would lead in delays and less significant results in DTO-BioFlow. The project is relying on development done in other initiatives and was not designed to do these developments.	DTO framework construction projects have a head start. Building an EU DTO is a political priority for the EU, and an expected outcome of the Mission, as such there is significant financial support for its timely implementation via the Horizon Europe and other EU funding mechanisms. Given the very close relationship between DTO-BioFlow partners and the most important related projects (with mutual partners holding prominent roles in linked projects, e.g., EDITO-Infra, Blue-Cloud, Modellab) alignment and co-development is ensured. Data, services & use-cases could first be tested/validated with the researchers before being transferred to the DTO frameworks.	01/09/2023			Active
17	New COVID variant or other viral infections causing pandemics, reducing working capacity, field work and travelling Likelihood: High / Severity: Medium	WP1-6	3	3	9	Delays/deviations in the delivery of related Deliverables and accomplishment of related Milestones.	Reschedule field and laboratory work and prioritize modelling and computational work; transfer all meetings, conferences and workshops online.	01/09/2023			Active
18	Stakeholder fatigue as a result of over-consultation from other projects/initiatives in the field.	WP6	2	4	8	Reluctance from users to engage in co-design of case studies, tools and services, reducing ultimate uptake and therefore project impact.	DTO-BioFlow partners have close links with other projects and initiatives in the field, therefore they can leverage these interactions and ensure there is not duplication of efforts so that the same	01/09/2023			Active

							stakeholders are not being called on excessively.			
19	Delays in hiring personnel or personnel dropping out of the project	WP1	2	2	4	Delays in the development of data products that would be integrated into the DTO. Delays in the completion of tasks and deliverables.	Maintaining clear communication with partners and with the European Commission. Ensuring that positions are filled in a timely manner.	01/09/2023		Active
20	Partner withdrawal from the Consortium	WP1	1	4	4	Partner contribution to tasks is missing. Deliverables or milestones cannot be completed.	Work gets re-distributed among the other Partners and they contribute to fulfilling the relevant deliverables/milestones, along with the relevant funding resources.	01/09/2023		Active
21	Failure to discover sleeping data: unable to identify and catalogue data that exists but is not documented	WP2	2	2	4	These resources will remain undiscovered for this project and any future initiative towards biodiversity data.	Communication of inventory and perceived gaps widely to project External Advisory Board (EAB) and WP6 stakeholders.	01/09/2023		Active
22	Refusal of data owners to share data	WP2	3	4	12	Necessary data to run analyses, models and develop data products are missing, thereby affecting the quality, coverage and relevance of the project deliverables.	Clear "Data policy and use" statement in the agreement with the data providers. WP2 Barriers playbooks (D2.2, M13 and D2.13, M36) compiles methods and strategies to address issues highlighted after the two data calls review processes. Use cases will be redesigned (adjusted) to become less complex and spatio-temporally less ambitious.	01/09/2023		Active

23	Lack of data mobilisation to the DTO due to the data's undetermined Access and Benefit Sharing (ABS) status	WP3	3	3	9	Reduced number of datasets that are compliant with the DTO's Ethics strategy (i.e. that are respecting the Nagoya protocol and ABS implementation) and this could be ingested into the DTO	For datasets with unclear ABS status, the ABS national focal points of each country will be contacted to ask for permission/authorization to use the respective data.	01/09/2023		Active
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